

School Facilities: Its Effects to Academic Performance of the College Student

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Abstract:

School facilities is essential to accomplishing educational goals and objectives as they provided for the physical and emotional need of teachers and students, and it was the major factor in ensured quality education. Teachers, for example, who wished to delivered instruction for the twenty-first century, must had access to scientific equipment and technical resources. When facilities undermine this, performance suffered. Many parted of the educational process relied on comfortable, safe settings as effective learned could not took placed without suitable school facilities. This study was to determine how the condition of school facilities affects student effectiveness in their academic performance. 327 students of a Local City College from the three departments of education, business, and technology selected as respondents used a proportionate random sample method in a descriptive quantitative questionnaire that adapted and validated. Based on the study's findings, facilities mentioned in the studied were already visible within the school environment these resources were not only perceptible but actively utilized by the students; nevertheless, there remained room for improvement as they had not yet undergone full updates aimed at enhanced the efficiency and effectiveness of the school facilities. This had slightly affected the academic performance of the students based on the results from the surveyed. Thus, researchers recommended conducting a surveyed and formulating a fundraising action planned to improve the proportionate sampling effectiveness and enhanced the school facilities for the better academic performance of both teachers and students.

Keywords: School Facilities, Academic Performances, Proportionate sampling Effectiveness and Proposed Enhancement

Introduction:

A school is a particular kind of educational establishment designed to provide pupils with classrooms. The ideal school is like the perfect home where the parent knows what is best for his child and provides for his needs. But with the excessively noisy and shortages of classrooms cause dissatisfaction and stress for students and teachers, impacting their ability to perform. Insufficiently noisy classrooms make students and teachers unhappy and stressed, which affects their performance. Air quality and lighting are other significant considerations that impact student academic performance. A poor school environment might also make it difficult for instructors to do their jobs. Teachers, for example, who wish to deliver instruction for the twenty-first century, must have access to scientific equipment and technical resources. When facilities undermine this, performance suffers. Jacoby (2004) stated that school facilities play a vital role in actualizing educational goals and objectives by satisfying the physical and emotional needs of the staff and students at the school. In this research, the researcher came up with a fundraising Action Plan. This Action Plan for facilities improvement is essential to enhance user experiences, meet evolving needs, ensure safety and compliance, achieve long-term cost savings, make a positive community impact, and leverage external support. By investing in the improvement of their facilities, organizations can create better spaces that align with their goals and better serve their users.

Review of Related Literature:

According to Alimi, Ehinola, and Alabi (2012), "education facilities" means to the entire school building, including classroom blocks, staff rooms, labs, workshop spaces, libraries, furniture, and other tangible items like stationery, electricity, and water. It also includes laboratory equipment, workshops, and playgrounds. The level of knowledge delivered to and acquired by pupils may vary depending on how schools plan for and maintain their educational facilities. This is due to the possibility that the educational environments to which kids are exposed could impact their academic success. Additionally, the actual physical structure of the buildings, school facilities also comprise a variety of building systems, such as plumbing, electrical, electricity, telecommunications, security, and fire suppression systems. The building's grounds and other amenities like sports fields, playgrounds, outdoor classrooms, parking, and vehicular access are all included in the facility, along with furniture, materials and supplies, equipment, and information technology by Jeffery A. Lackney in 2023.

Lack of classrooms, classroom congestion, low ventilation, and unhygienic, and packed canteens are signs of these subpar facilities, as are their unreliable operation or poor maintenance. Students do not forfeit their entitlement to a clean school because it is a public institution. Examples of this include the absence of canteens, poor ventilation, missing comfort rooms, and lack of tables and chairs in the classrooms use of outdated literature and

similar materials. Schneider (2002) examined the role that conducive conditions for safe, secure, comfortable, and healthy learning have on effective teaching and learning. He questioned whether facility characteristics most significantly influence academic results and, consequently, to what extent. It demonstrated that both student achievement and teacher effectiveness are significantly influenced by the state of the school's facilities. According to Toria (2003), school facilities significantly affect both instructors' and students' performance. The recruitment, retention, dedication, and effort of teachers are impacted by school facilities. Schools' physical environments have an impact on students' involvement, learning, and academic growth. Researchers typically draw the conclusion that it is very challenging to serve many children with complex needs in the absence of adequate facilities and resources. Academic performance, according to Narad and Abdullah (2016), is the knowledge gained that can be assessed by marks by a teacher or instructor and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be attained over the long term. They claimed that these goals are measured through continuous assessments or examination results.

Hansen (2000) states that all researchers have covered in their work the various elements that influence students' academic achievement. Both internal and external classroom elements, both of which have a significant impact on students' performance, can have an impact on students' academic success. The level of English proficiency of the students, class size, English textbooks, class test results, learning facilities, homework, the environment of the class, the difficulty of the course material, the role of the teacher in the class, the technology used in the class, and exam procedures are all internal classroom factors. Extracurricular activities, family issues, work, as well as problems with the economy, society, and other issues are examples of external classroom variables. According to studies, a variety of elements, including learning facilities, influence students' performance.

These studies typically focus on the physical infrastructure and resources within educational institutions and their impact on student learning outcomes, well-being, and overall educational experience. Numerous studies have highlighted the influence of school facilities on academic achievement. Factors such as classroom design, lighting, temperature, acoustics, and overall building conditions can significantly impact students. Effective facilities planning and management are essential for optimizing resources, maintaining infrastructure, and accommodating changing educational needs. Studies have examined strategies for efficient space utilization, maintenance practices, lifecycle cost analysis, and long-term planning to ensure well-functioning and cost-effective school facilities.

However, the overall synthesis highlights the significance of well-designed, safe, and supportive school facilities in fostering positive educational experiences and outcomes for students and educators alike.

Research Method:

The researcher employed the Descriptive Quantitative type of research. It is the process of gathering and interpreting numerical data, claims Voxco (20210). It can be used to identify trends and averages, formulate hypotheses, examine causality, and extrapolate findings to larger populations. Descriptive-quantitative research was used in the study. To make adequate and accurate interpretations of the data, descriptive research gathers, analyzes, categorizes, and tabulates information about current circumstances, practices, processes, trends, and cause-and-effect relationships (Calderon, 2006). For this study, a descriptive research design will be made to determine the level of effectiveness of school facilities.

Results and Discussion:

The result shown that the three - Education, Business and Technology " has the lowest weighted mean respectively, 2.19, 2.40 and 2.49 interpreted as Ineffective which implies that all departments agreed that each classroom's air conditioning is insufficient, which hinders students' ability to learned and causes them to lose interest and concentration when the air is too hot, lacking fresh air supply and inadequate temperature control can lead to discomfort among students and teachers. This the majority implies that it is widely acknowledged that the current air conditioning systems are insufficient to satisfy the basic requirements of both teachers and students. The effects of this kind of inadequacy go far beyond simple discomfort; they have a direct bearing on the classroom atmosphere, student participation, and general academic performance.

Table 1.
 Level of effectiveness of different school facilities perceived by the respondent.

Indicators	School of Education		School of Technology		School of Business	
	GWM	DE	GWM	DE	GWM	DE
Laboratory Equipment	2.42	I	3.09	E	2.80	E
Library	3.32	VE	3.22	E	3.23	E
Classroom ventilation	2.19	I	2.40	I	2.49	I
Canteen	2.30	I	2.46	I	2.75	E
Safety and Security	2.93	QS	2.74	QS	2.92	E

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Very Ineffective (VI), 1.76-2.50- Ineffective (I), 2.51-3.25- Effective (E), 3.26-4.00- Very Effective (VE), Weighted Mean – W.M., Descriptive Equivalent

Table shown, School of Technology has the highest general weighted mean (3.32), indicating Very Effective. The outcome is motivated by the fact that the students in this department credit the library staff's helpful assistance, and service for their academic progress and completion. Conversely, the variable "Classroom Ventilation" has the lowest weighted mean of all the variables. This suggests that all department concur that there is not enough air conditioning in each classroom, which makes it difficult for students to learn and makes them lose interest and concentration. Additionally, uncomfortable conditions for both students and teachers can result from a short supply of fresh air and inadequate temperature control. An article from the Wisconsin Department of Health Services supports the study's findings, which indicate that exposure to CO2 can have a range of negative health

impacts. These could include a coma, suffocation, convulsions, headaches, dizziness, restlessness, tingling or pins and needles, trouble breathing, sweating, exhaustion, a high heart rate, and high blood pressure. All of these could result in pupils learning less efficiently.

Table 2.
Effect of the School Facilities on the Academic Performance of the Students.

Indicators	SOE		SOT		SOB	
	GWM	DE	GWM	DE	GWM	DE
Intellectual Level	2.68	E	2.99	E	2.95	E
Personality	2.39	I	2.67	E	2.73	E
Motivation	2.74	E	3.17	E	2.89	E
Skills	2.7	E	2.96	E	2.90	E
Interest	2.81	E	2.89	E	2.88	E
Study Habit	2.8	E	2.83	E	2.95	E
Self-esteem	3.17	E	3.47	VE	3.09	E

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Very Ineffective (VI), 1.76-2.50- Ineffective (I), 2.51-3.25- Effective (E), 3.26-4.00- Very Effective (VE), Weighted Mean – W.M., Descriptive Equivalent

The table shown that the School of Technology, self-esteem had the highest general weighted mean. It indicates that the SOT student may come to the conclusion that the facility works really well for them as they use it. By trusting and believing in themselves to use the facilities to discover and experience new things, students utilize those facilities to enhance their self-esteem, grow, and develop as individuals. By contrast, the personality in the School of Education and Business believes that the library is the most efficient. Yet, the School Canteen’s “Canteen” has the lowest weighted mean of all the facilities, suggesting that it is devoid of essential furnishings, supplies, and equipment such as eating tables, seats, and even adequate sanitation and waste segregation.

Table 3.
Challenges Met by Students in Using the School Facilities.

Indicators	SOE		SOT		SOB	
	GWM	DE	GWM	DE	GWM	DE
Computer Laboratory	2.55	E	3.35	VE	2.74	E
Classroom Environment	2.35	I	2.75	E	2.68	E
Library	3.07	E	3.14	E	3.05	E
School Canteen	2.27	I	2.63	E	2.64	E

Legend: 1.00-1.75 – Very Ineffective (VI), 1.76-2.50- Ineffective (I), 2.51-3.25- Effective (E), 3.26-4.00- Very Effective (VE), Weighted Mean – W.M., Descriptive Equivalent

Table shown, Computer laboratory has the highest weighted mean in the School of Technology overall across all the factors. The fact that the pupils have not encountered any issues stems from the fact that the computer lab’s software and Microsoft version are both up-to-date. Similarly, the School of Education and Business believes that the library is the most efficient. Yet, the School Canteen’s “Canteen” has the lowest weighted mean of all the facilities, suggesting that it is devoid of essential furnishings, supplies, and equipment such as eating tables, seats, and even adequate sanitation and waste segregation.

Conclusion:

The researchers concluded that the majority of the school facilities are effective for the college students as they contribute to their academic success and completion, but on the other hand, they need to be improved and have additional school facilities to cater to the needs of the students. However, some facilities negatively impact the academic achievement of college students because of inadequate materials such as chairs, equipment, and tables, which hinder student ability to learn and cause them to lose interest and concentration. There is a need that the Mandaue City College must have their own school site. Applying Bronfenbrenner’s Ecological Systems Theory to studies on school facilities provides a holistic framework for understanding the multifaceted influences on academic performance, encompassing the immediate physical environment, interpersonal relationships, societal factors, and changes over time.

Recommendation:

The following suggestions were made based on the study’s findings and outcomes:

1. The school’s management and administration need to make plans and action through assessment and look for suggestions from the students to improve and enhance the whole aspect of the school, such as the comfort rooms, school clinic, and safety and security of the school.

- Gender-sensitive toilet with strong plan and policy is recommended. The availability of a clean water system for the bathroom is also encouraged. Regular supervision should be applied by concerned authorities to keep the toilet clean and maintain the schools' teaching-learning environment.

2. Majority of the structures require considerable repairs, restorations, retrofitting, and replacement of some essential components.
3. Future researchers related to school facilities that would involve the total population to gather additional insights on its significance especially involving teachers.
4. To conduct future studies using other research methods, specifically quantitative design, to assess if school facilities' condition significantly correlates to the student's academic performance.
5. Further studies involving qualitative methods employ phenomenology to explore the students' lived experiences in relation to school facilities.

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